

Early Civilization, Country Languages and Conflict Resolution in Africa

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ABSTRACT: Early civilization is a principle of many countries since everything tends to have a history of where everything began. The human race is associated with early civilization because the early man who was described as the homosapiens who later evolved to monkeys and to the now human race that is able to reason, strategize and control the activities of the Universe. Country languages are used to communicate and countries tends to have their internal languages such as tribal languages and inter-tribal languages differentiated by different dialects and different tones (Herber, 1989; Eriksen, 2022). Cross country languages are languages that are used to communicate between countries and global languages and are languages that are accepted globally which are majorly English and French. The objective of the study was to evaluate the relationship between early civilization, country languages and conflict resolution in Africa. An E-Questionnaire was administered to respondents from different countries which were then summarized and descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were estimated and interpreted and summarized in tables. Regression analysis was used to establish the relationships between the study aspects. The sub-objectives of the study were; to determine the effect of early civilization on conflict resolution in Africa, to establish the influence of country languages on conflict resolution in Africa, to establish the impact of early civilization on country languages in Africa and to finally establish the effect of early civilization, country languages and conflict resolution in Africa. Early civilization was measured using history; country languages was measured using dialect, tone, vernacular and English; while conflict resolution was measured using arbitration, court of law and out of court settlement. The study findings were that there is indeed early civilization in Africa as Africans have come along way historically even in terms of color and dress code. Many languages are used in different countries in Africa some of which are intra-country, others are inter-country, some are tribal languages, others are inter-tribal languages, yet others are intra-tribal languages. Countries such as Guinea Busau stated that they even have inter-family and intra-family languages. Globally accepted languages that Africans communicate with globally where found to be majorly English and French. Regression results revealed that early civilization significantly impacts on conflict resolution in Africa, early civilization influences country languages in Africa, country languages affects conflict resolution in Africa and collectively early civilization and country languages influences conflict resolution in Africa. The study findings are that there are countries with history and historical injustices associated with conflicts such as inter-tribal conflicts and even inter-country conflicts and experts in conflict resolution need to be engaged to resolve conflicts when they occur. Languages are crucial in conflict resolution since communicating effectively when resolving conflicts is important. Policies on history and historical injustices, country languages and conflict resolution are important in having stable countries in Africa.

INTRODUCTION

Early civilization was inferred to using history because history defines how far and where people have come from. Before civilization and later the colonial rule Africans were pure natives and were gathers in the forests that occupy many African countries. Following the colonization of the African continent by the whites, Africans were introduced to civilization and slowly by slowly they transited from being natives to becoming the modern man (Eriksen, 2022; Weaver, 1986; Herber, 1989). Some of the questions that linger in the world of early civilization are; should actors that are not officially authorized to make collectively binding decisions be part of conflict resolution, and how can their contributions to policy-making be identified if they are unseen? How can one authoritatively assess to what extent the country tribes and communities are affected by historical injustices? Which actors legitimately act as fire alarms and as account-holders to give an account of conflicts that have occurred in countries? Are certain communities' targets for historical injustices and do they influence the ability to diffuse policy outcomes to minimize conflicts? What is the role of professionals such as abattoirs and community leaders and what languages are effective in resolving conflicts? What is the responsiveness of the citizenry and what and whose interests collide with professional norms? Is the threat of sanctions indispensable to effective conflict management, or depending on the purposes, should the approaches to conflict resolution be more educational than punitive? By highlighting the core facets of the exercise and control of power through conflicts, the study of policy-makers' history raises crucial questions on the quality of conflict resolution, which targets the 'elephant in the forest' as

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explained by the public policy theory (Urbinati and Warren, 2008; Boin, 't Hart, Stern and Sundelius, 2005; Cichowski, 2013; Karsten, 2015; Miller, 2005; Ingram and Schneider, 2016). Most policies are made without consulting the constituents and without informing them to know which ones favour them but are made and implemented to favour leaders such as Counselors, Members of Parliament (MPs) and Governors (Brummel, 2021). Chiefs and sub-chiefs and other organs of administration of justice and injustices such as the police force enforce the law using their own mechanisms which usually are not preferred by the law abiders. Arbitrators sometimes step in to arbitrate in order to resolve conflicts but are forced to refer certain conflicts to the court of law and others are recommended to be settled out of court (Ansell and Gash, 2008; Bach, Van Thiel, Hammerschmid and Steiner; 2017). Conflict resolution is said to be undermined by several factors which are; community and tribal interests, land ownership, limited access to information and politics. Ruthlessly, political tribal leaders tend to buy goons to silence those who threaten their political interests while tribal leaders are keen on protecting the interests of the tribe including land ownership and land rights. It is not enough for the institutions under transformative constitutions to encourage conflicts of whatever nature and laws should be put in place to be used as benchmarks and foundation of resolution of conflicts (Thompson, 1980; Bertelli and Busuioc, 2021; León, Jurado and Madariaga, 2018).

The administration of justice and conflict resolution are political projects and in addition to addressing the historical injustices and getting dip into issues of early civilization conflict resolution should be handled with decorum it deserves (Dommett and Flinders, 2015; Esser and Strömbäck, 2014). Early civilization under the current dispensation is at the crossroads. Early civilization is usually associate with stone age and in this study was inferred using history. History and early civilization defines how far people have come and whether they can remember their ancient non-economic and economic activities, when conflicts started and whether they are able to go back to the roots when they used to live in harmony. Remembering history and its effectiveness in conflict resolution depends on the tribal architecture of the political system and the tribal superstructure since different tribes tend to have tribal dynamics. Demanding responsibility and strengthening cognitive bias, vertical and horizontal institutional and power fragmentation attenuate democratic power at the community level which can be scaled up to the tribal and further to the country level (Birkland, 2006; Hood, 2010; Hood, 2015; Knight, and Schwartzberg, 2020). The political incumbents such as governors of counties, Members of Parliament (MPs) (and their former counselors) and Members of the County Assemblies (MCAs) have a stake in the tribes that they lead and are sometimes either at the centre of inter-tribal conflicts or they at times fuel these conflicts to gain political mileage or to enhance incumbents' popularity and to sometimes work on those who they dislike in their constituencies (Manin, 1997; Mansbridge, 2003). Keane (2009) offered a more positive account in his book on 'monitory' democracy, in which he pointed out that 'the rapid growth of many different kinds of power scrutinizing mechanisms' and referred, in particular, to 'guardian' type institutions that use their claimed neutrality to appear as protectors of the public interest and to participatory mechanisms involving advocacy groups that act as 'surrogates' in their monitoring roles for the various populations and interests that they claim to represent (Raunio, and Hix, 2000; Bach, Van Thiel, Hammerschmid and Steiner, 2017; Hawkins and Jacoby, 2006).

An active abattoir regards themselves as a trustee of the state regime power and authority and assumes neutrality when arbitrating the conflicts at hand. Accordingly, he (she) usually defers to the executive and legislature, shuns appearance of policy making, supports patriarchy and other forms of violent exclusion, and overall "stability" over "change" (Peter, 2021; Piatak, Romzek, LeRoux and Johnston, 2018). An abattoir regards themselves as holding official power in fiduciary capacity for civil and democratic rights of all peoples, especially the disadvantaged, dispossessed and deprived. The abattoir does not regard adjudicatory power as a repository of the reason of state they constantly rework the distinction between the legal and political sovereign, in ways that legitimate arbitration action as an irreducible characteristic of activist adjudication; namely, that an abattoir remains possessed of inherent powers to mould the greater good of the society as a whole (Rudalevige, 2021; Fossheim, 2022; de Boer, 2022). These abattoirs however hear judgments in court as quite a number have their own law firms and they hear other court cases which are not necessarily cases of conflict resolution. Magistrates and judges have in some instances passed judgments about animal trespasses leave alone people fighting over boundaries of pieces of land because their scope of work is broad (Tetlock, 1991; Tetlock, 1992).

The tribesmen and tribeswomen who are the citizens (and who are also the electorate) and the political class need to rise to moral conviction so that they deliver the mandates of those who elected them and display ethical courage so that they donot ignore the protection of the very people who put them to the offices they occupy. Corruption is an enemy of economic development especially when integrated with ethnicity in which case it fuels electoral contests and compromises national stability (Blauberger and Kelemen, 2017; Hood, James, Jones, Scott and Travers, 1999). Many African countries tend to leverage on ethnicity as they tend to have multi-tribes some of which have a few domineering tribes with other tribes being the minority. The Kikuyus and Luos of Kenya, the Ibos of Nigeria, the Tutsis and Hutus of Rwanda and Burundi, the sub-tribes of Southern Sudan Republic, the communities of the Republic of Somalia, the Guinea Busau, Sierra Leon, the many tribes of South Africa including Kwa Zulu Natal, Malawi, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, Madagascar, Zanzibar, Republic of Togo, Ghana, Morocco, New Guinea, and even Israel where Jesus was born which prides of 12 tribes are countries which donot only have more

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than one tribe but has citizens who speak different languages. When you visit many of these countries they automatically tell you the ‘vernacular’ that is spoken there and which other languages are used for communication in the entire country.

Bureaucracy is the natural extension of the cabinet in the chain of delegation, and it is a policy-maker in its own right in the sense that decisions are made while taking into account the many levels that decisions are required to pass through before they are ratified. Many studies have demonstrated the roles of organized groups some by ‘programmatically elites’ and others by the less educated (such as the ‘Mungiki’ in Kenya) with clear views of the policy reforms that they believe must be carried out or of individual bureaucrats as policy ‘brokers’ who mediate between opposing coalitions and are active in the pursuit of compromise (Kriner and Schickler, 2017; Friedrich, 1940; Merkel, 2004; Romzek, LeRoux and Blackmar, 2012; Breaux, Perrewé, Hall, Frink, and Hochwarter, 2008). Even when the political environment is hostile bureaucracies of government must take different interacting factors into account, namely, the nature of the crisis, the institutional and political contexts and, actors’ strategies which they must clearly understand to remain as policy makers and implementers of policies in both favourable and hostile political regimes. Essentially, one should distinguish among the different outcomes of accountability processes especially as competing agendas may coexist, causing goal conflict between the goals of the electorate and the goals of political leaders whose balancing should be done by the administrative arm of justice (Stark, 2018; Tetlock and Lerner, 1999). In the case of the police who are charged with the responsibility for controlling and containing conflicts and calm riots in towns and in communities, they end up escalating the temperatures by beating, harassing and sometimes killing those who are involved in conflicts (“watu wa rungu” or “men of the big hard stick” as they are called) creating bad air between the rioters and other perpetrators and the police force (Braithwaite, 1997; Romzek and Ingraham, 2000; Schillemans, Overman and Fawcett, 2021a). Essentially then, sanctioning those who are associated with historical injustices is different from triggering policy change, and both may be unrelated; policy change will not have the same scope if it stems from genuine learning from failures or from superficial strategic adjustment. The post-conflict scenario in the long-term and its consequences should be evaluated, but it is difficult to anticipate if a crisis will be ‘fast-burning’ with a return to ‘business as usual’ or if there will be ‘a crisis after the crisis’ so that measures can be put in place to prevent other crises from occurring in future (Wood, Matthews, Overman and Schillemans, 2022; Pollitt and Hupe, 2011). Sometimes professionals are involved in conflict resolution after which they do the post-crisis assessment to get an indication as whether the conflicts were resolved properly and whether there are likely to be other conflicts in future including whether they should be resolved the same way or other methods should be adopted in resolving them. When historically conflicts have been there, when do they occur? In many African countries conflicts tend to occur around the general election but how quickly public attention will move on to other concerns immediately after the general elections and the timing (how quickly or how slowly) matters more generally if we think, for example, of the tighter or looser connection with the electoral cycle. Political parties especially the ones that do not win the elections in most cases do not agree with the outcome of the elections and riots tend to follow to dispute the outcome which sometimes ends in the court of law (Fawcett, Flinders, Hay and Wood, 2017; Papadopoulos, 2012).

Checks that impose restraints with the goal of avoiding abuses of power and, more generally, control of an institution by other institutions in the same political system that is grounded on the doctrine of separation of powers are commonly included in the category of horizontal accountability (Sørensen and Torfing, 2021; Finer, 1941; Fortunato, Martin, and Vanberg, 2019). Conflicts between countries and conflicts between tribes and communities in the same country are common and are resolved according to the laid down procedures of conflict resolution. By increasingly acting as instances of horizontal accountability, courts indirectly gain influence in the legislative process, as it is rational for policy-makers to anticipate their views as the courts follow the due process. Such interference by the unelected has been criticized, but one should keep in mind that politicians may be able to influence the outcome of the solution or outcome of conflict resolution (Alter, Helfer and Madsen, 2018; Sørensen, 2020; Stimson, Mackuen and Erikson, 1995; Montanaro, 2017; Grossman, 2022; Kam, Bertelli and Held, 2020). Legislative bodies play a critical role in resolving conflicts and through hearings, inquiries, and investigations, legislators can hold leaders of communities accountable for their conduct especially if they lead the communities in such a way that living in harmony is not emphasized. Brokerage of country conflicts by international courts such as The Hague calls for involvement of country leaders at the highest level especially if they are implied in being part of those who are behind disagreements. Frictions between countries have led to war such as the case in the Middle East and the war in Ukraine. The judiciary can also hold political leaders accountable by reviewing the legality of their actions as courts can rule against decisions that violate laws or constitutional provisions justifying the existence of the courts of law (to hear cases and pass judgments on conflict resolution) (Tetlock, 1991; Immergut, 1992; León, 2018). The so-called judicialization of politics means that courts become policy actors by being asked to arbitrate on policy controversies, even if they do not aim to advance any particular policy preferences. By acting as veto players capable of striking down legislation (regardless of their motivations), courts become pivotal actors and indirectly take over legislative functions. Like the shadow of future elections that incentivizes incumbents to be responsive to voters’ preferences, the shadow of court rulings perceived as likely to reverse legislation prompts elected officials to absorb the preferences attributed to the judiciary (Yeung and Lodge 2019). In the United States, for example, a newer area of interbranch bargaining research incorporates the judicial branch into the model of separation of powers in which the legislators seek to reach decisions that are as close as possible to their own preferences but robust to court

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interference (Knight and Schwaetzberg, 2020; Romzek, LeRoux and Blackmar, 2012; Arceneaux and Vander Wielen, 2017). There are political struggles in the Judiciary itself based on each judicial officer's intellectual, ideological, political, social, and cultural position in which case then the judicial officers should be seen to be independent as individuals. How they handle cases of resolving conflicts as abattoirs, as judges, magistrates and advocates and how they advice on the out of court settlements goes along way in reducing future conflicts. Judicial officers are essentially politicians and whether their politics emerges from their judgements or their extrajudicial scholarly writings and speeches, judicial officers have consigned the Judiciary to what has been described by judicial experts as institutional political actors since that is how they retain their seats as Court Marshalls in the first place. They are all political seats which they use to pass judgements some of which are on conflict resolution any way (Tsebelis, 2003; de Vries and Solaz, 2017; Marsden, 2011; Miller and Whitford, 2016).

History contends that political vision is not wholly liberal but has some radical ingredients of social democracy (with pillars of decentralizing the imperial presidency, the whole gamut of rights, devolution, equitable distribution of power, democratizing and decolonizing state's machinery of violence, its values and principles) including the participation of the people in the affairs of the state and that is the politics judicial officers are supposed to do. Therefore after judicial officers struggle against the various pressures inimical to their independence (executive, parliament, corporate and civil society, cartels, ethnic communities, religion, family, relatives, and friends) to achieve their individual independence, a further struggle ensues that addresses the question in whose interest and independence is exercised whether to itself or to the individual judicial officers (Vanberg, 2015; Urbinati and Warren, 2008; Svallfors, 2020). Their mission is to safeguard the rule of law and protect minorities and individuals from violations of their rights and, more generally, to ensure compliance with principles of good governance (Raymond and DeNardis, 2015). It is sometimes remarked that ombudsman institutions' lack of a formal 'bite' can be offset through creative operation (for instance, with an active communication policy) that pressures public authorities to comply and agree with those who are given the responsibility of protecting the rights of others (Bovens and Wille, 2021).

As it were there is need to give credit to the quite nuanced conclusions of psychological research regarding accountability's impact on the feelings and the behaviour of individuals who are held accountable (Peters and Nagel, 2020; Flinders, 2012; Goodhart, 2011). This body of work shows that the reactions of individuals are shaped by a whole range of moderating factors, whereas studies of politics are, perhaps unduly, more assertive when they assume, for example, that politicians can decipher the preferences of accountability forums and adjust to them (Rudalevige, 2021; Jordana, Fernández-i-Marín and Bianculli, 2018). As the validity of such beliefs about policy-makers' attitudes and behavioural choices has been insufficiently tested until now, the study of accountability in politics would undoubtedly be improved by a careful incorporation of more evidence from social and organizational psychology (Healy, Malhotra and Moe, 2010). This element intended to show that cross-fertilization between various relatively insulated research communities is indeed indispensable to capture the prismatic nature of accountability. Studying policy-makers' accountability requires navigating arenas of governance that have varying properties, such as codification or visibility. It also requires looking at the role of institutions that we must not forget are populated by actors and, therefore, do not necessarily work as intended on paper, just as they do not always produce the expected results (Gersen and Stephenson, 2014; Philp, 2009; Garoupa, and Ginsburg, 2015; Fortunato, Martin, and Vanberg, 2019). An interactionist approach highlights the existence of complex accountability webs, involving various types of individual and collective actors in their roles as account-givers and account-holders, whose interdependence stems from different organizing principles that coexist, sometimes in a conflicting way, such as hierarchy, delegation, control, antagonism or cooperation. Furthermore, time matters, and accountability fluctuates between periods of routine and equilibrium and critical episodes of high dramatic intensity, in which vulnerabilities and defenses come to light especially as reputations are called into question, but they can be used as a shield to protect oneself from criticism (Gasper and Reeves, 2011; Mechkova, Lührmann and Lindberg, 2019; Busuioac, 2021; McCubbins and Schwartz, 1984).

Despite the growing use of voting advice applications, there are generally relatively vague profiles of parties and candidates in mind and simply diffuse expectations from the representatives. Unsurprisingly, then, discretion is inherent to representative government, and principal-agent theory has convincingly demonstrated that delegation by a principal usually leads to the discretionary power of his or her agent if the contractual metaphor is applied to describe delegation mandates, apart from being implicit, the contract is an incomplete one, with many points remaining unspecified (Potter, 2019; Peters, 2017; Peters, 2021). Therefore, in representative democracies, elections are also a mechanism of after election accountability: the threat of electoral sanction should incentivize office-holders to keep their promises to voters so that citizens retain some of their self-determination despite their decision-making power being delegated (Marvel and Girth, 2016; Goodin, 2007; Mortensen, 2016; Koliba, Mills, and Zia, 2011; Jordana, 2017). If incumbents discount the risk of being defeated in the next election, for example, in the absence of credible alternatives or because their electorate displays strong partisan loyalty – office-holders would have no incentives to remain responsive to the voters who elected them and temporarily authorized them to rule (Jacobs, 2011; Hill and Lynn, 2005; McGraw and Dolan, 2007). If the promises of the electorate are not met the electorate sometimes turn to violence because of wanting to challenge the outcome and to demand what they were promised during the campaigns even if the promises were too ambitious.

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Internationally, the International Criminal Court at the Hague has been instrumental in resolving conflicts in many countries in which conflicts have occurred following general elections that are usually contested sometimes because of not wanting to concede defeat (Alter, Helfer

and Madsen, 2018). However, empirical research also suggests that voters encounter cognitive limitations since whoever wins they take it that it is the responsibility of the leadership in place to protect its citizens in addition to providing the requisite goods and services. Findings from survey and experimental research indicate that people use shortcuts to make their decisions on political matters especially when they want quick wins. They use heuristics, such as party cues (for example, 'Mlolongo' or Voter queing which was embraced during the era of President Daniel arap Moi in Kenya with the intention of directing voters who to vote for), the opinions of friends, media frames (where the media consistently focus on particular personalities to intimidate them) or the positions of interest groups and even more so for those (generally those who are less educated) who lack familiarity with politics sometimes reduce upper-class bias in participation in public affairs which may lead to inadequate conclusions and poorly informed choices (Hajer, 2009; Hameleers, Bos and de Vreese, 2019). Shortcuts are instrumental in overcoming informational shortfalls and making decisions despite the complexity of political matters but do not protect against evaluation and attribution errors due to bounded rationality (such as overemphasizing recent events or overweighting incumbents' broken pledges).

However, as preexisting views of the world serve as perceptual screens, responsibility judgements are biased by prior political beliefs because 'people prefer to give credit for good outcomes to political actors they already like and are equally willing to blame poor outcomes on political actors they already dislike' (Hohendorf, Saalfeld and Sieberer, 2021; Vandamme, 2018). For example, partisanship colours and party slogans and perceptions of experts on the economic situation as to who is responsible for the good or bad state of the economy including fueling riots to counter high prices and poor economic performance is witnessed in many African countries. Findings from a study based on data from twenty-five democracies across an array of policy areas, including the economy, social welfare, immigration and national security, confirm that holding governments accountable for past performance is mainly the prerogative of highly sophisticated citizens (deVries and Gigerde, 2014; Langvatn and Holst, 2022; Ingold and Varone, 2012; Bianculli, Jordana and Fernández-i-Marín, 2015). At the same time, however, the sophistication gap narrows when voters attach a higher degree of salience to a policy area, that is, when the issues at stake are important to them. Banditry, which is a criminal act of citizens who access fire arms and terrorize communities of their own countries, and cattle rusting in countries where livestock is a precious asset are mediated upon to resolve. Illegal logging in forests are condemned by forest Rangers and sometimes trigger running battles between the Rangers and those who want to cut trees. Essentially clobbering by police of slum dwellers of many African countries during country unrests are common practices of many countries in Africa.

Studies that have been done all concur that multilevel structures risk undermining responsibility attribution and thus democratic accountability and the associated complexity of multilevel arrangements usually goes far beyond the formal distribution of power. The thinking is that the opposition may 'bark' as expected in a logic of adversarial partisan politics but is not able to 'bite'. In some instances the opposition is bought or compromised so that it sings the song of the government in power. In situations of 'divided government' in which different parties control the presidency and Congress, the existence of a regime of power separation incentivizes each branch to be sensitive to the preferences of the other branch (Auel and Benz, 2005; Jacobs and Schillemans, 2016; Kuipers and Brändström, 2020). Allocating responsibility may be even more difficult when the government is divided, as in presidential systems with different majorities in the executive and the legislative resulting in a relatively weak government facing a strong 'veto point', or when the legislature is bicameral, with two differently composed chambers (Immergut, 1992; Tsebelis, 2003; Royed, Leyden and Borrelli, 2000; Koop, 2014; Koop and Lodge, 2020). This mechanism is designed to ensure the smooth coexistence of 'policy representation' and 'public responsiveness' and therefore to remain in power, governments are incentivized to adjust their policy choices to citizens' preferences, and citizens in turn adjust their views to consider the existing supply of policies (the erosion of partisan identities and the prevalence of issue voting facilitating flexibility). In addition, representation is 'dynamic' governments use policies to respond to perceived shifts in public opinion, and policies generate feedback effects, with voters also modifying their preferences depending on the changes they discern in governmental action and the outcomes thereof (Mechkova, Lührmann and Lindberg, 2019; Peters, 2014; James, Jilke, Petersen and Van de Walle, 2016; Jordana, Fernández-i-Marín and Bianculli, 2018; Hupe and Edwards, 2012).

The policy process is often interactive, polycentric and unavoidably messy, with policy complexity mirroring and responding to societal and problem complexity. Political decisions are formulated or implemented through bargaining or deliberation between actors who 'coopete' in diffuse policy networks, involving not only politicians and administrators but also interest representatives, stakeholders and experts (independent or members of advocacy coalitions). Therefore, governance becomes less public, less vertical and more interdependent. 'Coproduction' or 'collaborative governance' are the usual descriptions of such policy-making modes, referring to collaboration with non-governmental actors, vertical intergovernmental cooperation across jurisdictional layers or a combination of both (Williams, Van Dooren, Christensen and Laegreid, 2017; Papadopoulos, 2012; Fossheim, 2022; Caplan, Crampton,

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Grove, and Somin, 2013; Carpenter and Mosse, 2013). Sometimes, collaborative modes have been adopted to remedy the flaws of purely managerialist governance, and in many cases, collaborative governance also has normative value with respect to pluralism and inclusiveness. However, from a democratic perspective, it is problematic if elected officials are unevenly engaged in collaborative policy-making arenas, as shown by a comparative study of a large number of cases across countries and jurisdictional levels (Bertelli, 2016; Tilley and Hobolt,

2011; Sørensen, Hendriks, Hertting and Edelenbos, 2020). The most influential actors may not be officially authorized to make collectively binding decisions: they may not be visible, possibly leading to errors in the allocation of responsibilities, or may be unelected, so that the wielding of power is divorced from democratic accountability in which instructions and directives emanate from sources which are unseen and which are not known. The movement towards collaborative governance in many countries is prominently manifested in the advent of various modes of cooperation not only in public service delivery but also in communities where the majority of the population are entrenched. (Emerson, Nabatchi and Balogh, 2012; Cairney, Heikkila and Wood, 2019; Maricut-Akbik, 2020; Grube, 2019; Huber and Shipan, 2002; Hobolt, Tilley and Banducci, 2013).

Another major trend is the delegation of tasks to independent agencies that have been entrusted with considerable authority, most notably over economic and risk regulation but also more generally over service delivery and policy implementation. In particular, regulatory agencies – such as competition authorities or those in charge of the utilities sector – become crucial players with strong law-making roles in their area of competence (Carpenter and Krause, 2007; Vibert, 2007; Hood, Jennings and Copeland, 2016) so that their growth has been portrayed as ‘the rise of the unelected’ (König, Felfeli, Achtziger. and Wenzelburger, 2022).

In the European Union, for example, national agencies become part of a multilevel administrative space through their participation in EU-wide rule-enforcing and coordination networks. This amplifies centrifugal trends within national executives because national agencies operate at arm’s length from governments and tend to become ‘double-hatted’ by developing loyalties with respect to EU institutions (Auel, Rozenberg and Tacea, 2015; Christensen and Lægheid, 2017; Culpepper, 2010; Majone, 2001). It then becomes that the ‘many eyes’ problem, which may undermine the effectiveness of individual agencies’ accountability, combines with the ‘many hands’ problem. In such a shared administrative space, responsibility is diluted, and informational asymmetries that obstruct public scrutiny are particularly difficult to overcome in multilevel settings (Thompson, 1980; Bach, Ruffing and Yesikagit, 2015; Egeberg and Trondal, 2009; Posner and Vermeule, 2011; Pollitt and Hupe, 2011; Schillemans, 2011; Brummel, 2021; Apaydin and Jordana, 2020; Boer, 2022). The determinant here is forum drift, which often relates to information gaps due to goal conflict or to intentional inactivity because of limited time and attention and of other more pressing priorities. Policy salience seems to be necessary for forums to become active and what counts perhaps even more is the existence of exceptional focusing events that damage the reputation of agencies by subjecting them to ‘emotionalized blame attribution’ by fixing blame on the wrong person when the culprits are dancing and dinning and thumbing their chests as to how easy it is to escape from the mess they created - they comfortably tell you ‘bye-bye’ without wanting to know how much it hurts! alarm!alarm!alarm! (Iyengar, 1991; Tetlock and Lerner, 1999; Cutler, 2008; O’Donnell, 1998; Halachmi, 2014; Boin,‘t Hart and McConnell, 2009; Hasler, Küebler and Marcinkowski, 2016; Opperhuizen, Klijn and Schouten, 2020).

Studies on policy controversies that gave birth to blame games in the UK, Germany and Switzerland by Hinterleitner (2017) and Hinterleitner (2020) who distinguished between ‘high stakes’ and ‘below the radar’ blame games leading to different outcomes. The author found that the public salience of issues and the institutional terrain, including informal and implicit game rules, shape the space in which conflict management occurs by providing blaming gateways and barriers against blame. In the British political system, for example, restrictive conventions about resignation (and more generally responsibility attribution) ‘clearly benefit incumbents during blame games’ with limited incentives for the government to amend failed policies; in contrast, in Germany, extensive conventions of resignation are, among others, ‘conducive to creating a rather aggressive blame game that centers on political incumbents’ (Savoie, 2008; Gomez and Wilson,

2008). This stands at odds with the conventional knowledge about the conflictual Westminster-style bipartisan politics in the United Kingdom and the more accommodative style of German politics related to coalition government and institutional fragmentation (Vis, 2016; Bach, Ruffing

and Yesilkagit, 2015). Another research focused essentially on economic voting – initially in the United States, and then with a comparative approach and it established that, whether voters are concerned with their individual well-being (egocentric voting) or with the state of the economy of their country as a whole (sociotropic voting), they do reward or sanction governments depending on their evaluations and may decide to go to the streets immediately after the election results are announced (Grigorescu, 2015; Maravall and Sanchez-Cuenca, 2009). Studies on the relationship between early civilization and conflict resolution had the intention of finding out whether there were conflicts in the past, how they were resolved and whether these conflicts have reduced and whether they are now easier or more difficult to resolve especially after taking into account the different languages that are used for communication in different African countries. The questions that arise are; Is history important in conflict resolution in African countries? What is the role of country languages in conflict resolution in Africa? Are country languages associated with country history or early civilization or have languages evolved over the years in African countries? Collectively does history and country

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languages influence conflict resolution in Africa? This study evaluates the influence of early civilization and country languages on conflict resolution in Africa.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Early civilization recognizes that the world was conquered historically in the stone age and that the human person has evolved over the years. Early civilization means that people living in tribes are calm and peaceful and exhibit minimal tribal conflicts because if their forefathers were peaceful, history dictates that they should be peaceful as well. Conflicts have however been associated with many African countries where tribal clashes and displacement of communities has dominated many African tribes particularly after the country general election or inter and intra-tribal conflicts. History tends to contend that every person has an origin and therefore every person belongs somewhere. Some countries in Africa have a history of conflicts such as inter-country conflicts, intra-country conflicts and tribal conflicts. Conflicts have been reported in many African countries and the need to resolve the conflicts have been given priority by countries where conflicts have occurred. History judges some of these countries harshly because the international community steps in to address country issues and sometimes sends professional conflict resolution experts to assist them to resolve conflicts in their countries. The Republic of Somalia, Southern Sudan, The Democratic Republic of Congo, Ruanda, Burundi and even Kenya have been associated with conflicts. Even in countries that are known to be politically stable such as Tanzania and Kenya have also sometimes recorded conflicts especially during the electioneering years. Countries such as The Independent Republic of Somalia where the Somalis fought amongst themselves and tore their own country apart and countries such as the Southern Sudan which have experienced instability for many years even after attaining self rule are examples of countries that have experienced conflicts. Republics of Ruanda and Burundi where there were the fights between the Tutsis and the Hutus which lead to deaths of many citizens of those countries is a trend of concern in the entire African continent (Alter, Helfer and Madsen, 2018; Grube, 2019).

Languages are a means of communication within and outside countries. The globally accepted language is English which communicates across the globe and which is accepted in written documentation and oral communication. French comes second to English such that those who do not come from English Speaking Countries can communicate in French (Francophone countries). Within regions such as the East African Region or the West African Region, they have the languages that they embrace as a region. Kiswahili for example is a National Language for The Republic of Tanzania and also for the Country Kenya. Each country has their own Vernacular(s) as in the case of Nigeria (Yoruba), South African vernacular, Uganda Vernacular and the many Vernacular Languages that there are in Kenya and other African countries. In fact quite a number of African Countries internally have more than one vernacular language some of which have multiple dialects. When resolving conflicts the languages that are used are the languages that are understood by those who are being arbitrated on. The courts tend to embrace the national languages and in the case of international courts they use the English language. The tribal conflicts in African countries that have tribes are settled using vernacular languages that are understood at that level. Country languages are an important enabler for conflict resolution because there is need for the those who sit at the table to resolve conflicts to communicate in a language that both parties understand. Global conflicts are handled using English language except for the French Speaking Countries (Francophone Countries) where French is an accepted media of communication. Intra-country conflicts are addressed using country vernacular languages or other languages that are accepted for mediation (Vis, 2016; Maestas, Atkeson, Croom and Bryant, 2008; Birkland, 2006).

A large body of literature, according to some scholars, has focused on the idea that taking stock of happenings in history and historical injustices are essential in helping to cut down on inter-tribal conflicts. The relationship between history and conflict resolution is well documented in Kenya as when Kofi Anan travelled to Kenya to broker political temperatures because the political leaders were almost tearing each other and the country apart because 'they had agreed to disagree'. The journey to the Hague by the Kenyan Leaders reminded Kenyans that even country leaders can be sanctioned and they were expected to be accountable to the citizens who put them in power (Lindsay, 2017). Leaders who are transparent and accountable are more trusted by those who elected them since they tend to have confidence that they take care of the country resources entrusted on them. South Korea's Board of Audit and Inspection and Indonesia's centralized service delivery portals exemplify how transparency can enhance public trust and improve accountability and by extension minimize inter and intra country conflicts. Moreover, holding country managers accountable strengthens country integrity and reinforces adherence to the rule of law. The experiences of countries like Singapore and New Zealand highlight how measures aimed at reducing corruption and increasing responsiveness to citizen needs lead to more legitimate and credible governance structure where there were minimal conflicts (Schmidt, 2020; Svallfors, 2020). Similarly, Germany's robust legal framework underscores the importance of checks and balances in preventing abuse of power and promoting accountability. Participatory budgeting initiatives in Brazil and social audits conducted under India's MGNREGA program demonstrate how involving citizens in governance processes enhances resource management, service delivery, and public participation. This research sought to establish the influence of early civilization and country languages on conflict resolution in Africa.

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CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypotheses Testing

- H0 : Early Civilization has no effect on conflict resolution in Africa.
- H02: Early Civilization has no influence on country languages in Africa.
- H03: Country languages have no impact on conflict resolution in Africa.
- H04: Early Civilization and country languages have no impact on conflict resolution in Africa.

Materials and Methods

Data on early civilization, country languages and conflict resolution was collected using an E-Questionnaire. Questions about peoples’ identities and how far in the past they can remember including how their economic and non-economic activities have evolved over the years were all aggregated and the mean and standard deviation tabulated. The data was rated on a 5-likert scale and respondents were interviewed electronically. Tests of dispersion and measures of central tendency were estimated. Data was also ranked in order of priority. Data was then analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. This approach of qualitative data analysis tools are as recommended by Bogdan and Biklen (2003) and Douglas and Francis (2002). The analyzed data was displayed in tables. The following is the estimated model that was used to determine how the independent variable(s) impact on the dependent variable:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2$$

Where:

Y = Conflict Resolution

X₁ = Early Civilization

X₂ = Country Languages

β₀ = Constant term

β₁ = regression coefficients for X₁

β₂ = regression coefficients for X₂

β₁ and **β₂** are coefficients

ε = the error term

Four regression equations were estimated. The first regression was to establish the effect of early civilization on conflict resolution in Africa and was stated as follows.

$$\text{ConflResolv} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EarlCivic} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where, ConflResolv is conflict resolution and EarlCivic is early civilization, **β₁** is the coefficient and **β₀** is the constant term.

The second equation was estimated to determine the effect of early civilization on country languages in Africa and was stated as follows.

$$\text{CountryLags} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EarlCivic} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where, CountryLags is country languages and EarlCivic is early civilization, **β₁** is the coefficients and **β₀** is the constant term.

The third regression estimated the impact of country languages on conflict resolution in Africa and the equation was stated thus as;

$$\text{ConflResolv} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{E CountryLags} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where, ConflResolv is conflict resolution and CountryLags is country languages, **β₁** is the coefficient and **β₀** is the constant term.

The fourth equation was estimated to determine the effect of early civilization and country languages on conflict resolution in Africa and was stated as follows.

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$$\text{ConflResolv} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EarlCivic} + \beta_2 \text{CountryLags} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where, ConflResolv is conflict resolution, CountryLags is country languages and EarlCivic is early civilization, β_1 is and β_2 are the coefficients and β_0 is the constant term.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Descriptive statistics

The variables of the study were early civilization, country languages and conflict resolution. Early civilization was measured through history, country languages were measured using dialect, tone of language, national language and the English language, while conflict resolution was measured using rule of law, arbitration and out of court settlements. E-questionnaires which contained 5-likert scale questions for ticking while others were straight questions which required straight short answers were sent to respondents in selected African countries. Some responded and sent them back via emails, others were provided with a link for accessing the questionnaire, others provided websites where the questionnaires could be sent and quite a number filled the questionnaire and provided details on how to access the filled questionnaire while others answered the questions patiently over their telephones (telephone booths, landlines, cell phones or ‘walki-talki’) In fact one interviewee did the telephone interview from a forest in Malawi where he was cutting trees for future firewood for sale while another interviewee answered the questions from his farm in Lilongwe, yet another respondent was interviewed from Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) in Congo forest. 40 questionnaires were sent to respondents considered sufficient to form a basis for analysis and interpretation of results. The responses were used to qualitatively quantify the independent variables (early civilization and country languages) and the dependent variable (conflict resolution). The variables of the 5-likert scale were averaged and summarized in the table 1.

Table 1: Early Civilization, Country Languages and Conflict Resolution

	Mean	Std Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
ConflResolv	1.8176	0.6250	0.2934	1.1956
EarlCivic	3.2191	0.2364	-1.0216	2.7825
CountryLags	2.1619	0.1598	0.4313	0.3267

Source: Researcher, 2026

Conflict resolution had a mean of 1.8176 with a standard deviation of 0.6250 which was considered moderate and was skewed to the right and was normally distributed. Early civilization had a mean of 3.2191 which was quite high with a low standard deviation of 0.2364. Country languages recorded a mean of 2.1619 and a low mean of 0.1598. The data observations for conflict resolution was skewed to the right and normally distributed, the data observations on early civilization was skewed to the left but was not normally distributed while the data observations on country languages was skewed to the right and was normally distributed.

Table 2: Conflict Resolution

ConflResolv	Mean	Std Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Rule of law	0.2468	0.0681	-1.0572	0.9276
Arbitration	1.9473	0.8596	1.9374	1.3627
Out of Court Settlement	3.2586	0.9472	0.0000	1.2964
Averages	1.8176	0.6250	0.2934	1.1956

Source: Researcher, 2026

Table 2 shows that the Rule of law had a mean of 0.2468 with little standard deviation of 0.0681. Arbitration recorded a mean of 1.9473 with an average mean of 0.8596 and out of court settlement estimated a high mean of 3.2586 and a standard deviation of 0.9472. Data observations for rule of law were skewed to the left, data observations for arbitration were skewed to the right, while data observations for the out of court settlement were skewed to the right and to the left (in other words at the middle). The data observations for rule of law, arbitration and out of court settlement were normally distributed. The aggregate of the means of conflict resolution was an average of 1.8176 with a standard deviation of 0.6250 and skewness to the right and normally distributed.

Table 3: Early Civilization

EarlCivic	Mean	Std Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
History	3.2191	0.2364	-1.0216	2.7825

Source: Researcher, 2026

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The means, standard deviations and skewness and kurtosis of the descriptive statistics of the values of early civilization were calculated. The respondents rated the aspect of history or early civilization very highly. The mean of history was a high of 3.2191 with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.2364 with data observations skewed to the left with the data observations not normally distributed.

Table 4: Country Languages

CountryLags	Mean	Std Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Dialect	1.4852	0.5827	1.1673	0.9454
Tone	0.2555	0.0268	0.0918	1.2176
Vernacular	2.2747	0.1654	-1.4859	-1.6156
National language	3.1456	0.0154	2.3147	1.0534
English	3.6487	0.0087	0.0684	0.03241
Averages	2.16194	0.1598	0.43126	0.326642

Source: Researcher, 2026

Country languages were disaggregated into dialect, tone, vernacular, national language and English language. Dialect had a mean of 1.4832 and a standard deviation of 0.5827, tone had a low mean of 0.2555 and a low standard deviation of 0.0268, vernacular recorded a slightly high mean of 2.2747 with a low standard deviation of 0.1654, with the national language estimating a high mean of 3.1456 and a very low standard deviation of 0.0154 and finally the global English language estimated the highest mean of 3.6487 and very small standard deviation of 0.0087. In terms of skewness, data observations on dialect, tone, national language and the English language were skewed to the right while the data observations of vernacular were skewed to the left. In total, the data observations for all the aspects of country languages (dialect, tone vernacular, national language and English language) were all normally distributed. The average of the values of the different aspects resulted to an aggregate mean of country languages of 2.16194 with a low average standard deviation of 0.1598 with skewness to the right with data normally distributed.

REGRESSION RESULTS

The Effect of Early Civilization on Conflict Resolution

Early civilization was regressed against conflict resolution and the results are tabulated in table 6. The coefficient of correlation stood at 43.3% indicating that there is a positive relationship between early civilization and conflict resolution. The coefficient of determination of ($r=0.313$) is a testament that 31.3% of conflict resolution is explained by early civilization and this explanation is significant as given by the F-value of 45.251 and a significance p-value of 0.000 ($p=0.000$).

Table 5: Early Civilization and Conflict Resolution

Model Summary								
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate				
1	.433 ^a	.313	.276	3.44313				
a. Predictors: (Constant), Governance								
ANOVA ^a								
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.		
1	Regression	84.348	1	44.274	45.251	.000 ^b		
	Residual	32.367	34	4.063				
	Total	116.715	35					
a. Dependent Variable: Conflict Resolution								
b. Predictors: (Constant), Early Civilization								
Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.0456	.6417		1.2654	.0469	-1.4213	2.1344
	Early Civilization (EarlCivic)	3.4267	1.7532	.8354	1.1347	.000	1.2474	2.5467
a. Dependent Variable: Conflict Resolution (ConflResolv)								

Source: Researcher, 2026

The constant term of 2.0456 is significant as denoted by the t-value and p-value ($t=1.2654$, $p=0.0469$) meaning that conflicts can still be resolved without taking into account history and historical injustices. The coefficient term of 3.426 of early civilization infers

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that 3.426 units of history accounts for only one unit of conflict resolution which means that the biggest proportion of conflict resolution is explained by other factors other than history. The coefficient value of early civilization of 3.426 is significant ($t=1.134$, $p=.000$). The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that early civilization does not have a significant effect on conflict resolution in Africa.

$$\text{ConflResolv} = 2.0456 + 3.426\text{EarlCivic}$$

Where ConflResolv is conflict resolution and EarlCivic is early civilization.

The Effect of Early Civilization on Country Languages

Early civilization was regressed against country languages and the estimates revealed that there is a positive relationship between early civilization and conflict resolution as denoted by correlation coefficient of 54.2% ($R=0.542$). The coefficient of determination of ($R\text{-Square}=0.447$) is a testament that 44.7% of country languages is explained by early civilization and this explanation is significant as given by the F-value of 49.2733 and a significance p-value of 0.000 ($p=0.000$).

Table 6: Early Civilization and Country Languages

Model Summary								
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate				
1	.542 ^a	.447	.343	4.64413				
a. Predictors: (Constant), Early Civilization								
ANOVA ^a								
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.		
1	Regression	87.326	1	74.348	49.2733	.000 ^b		
	Residual	32.463	34	3.143				
	Total	119.789	35					
a. Dependent Variable: Country Languages								
b. Predictors: (Constant), Early Civilization								
Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-2.1356	.6425		-1.3754	.8348	-1.2143	2.1434
	Early Civilization (EarlCivic)	2.3645	3.3743	.76879	4.2541	.0000	1.1132	4.3647
a. Dependent Variable: Country Languages								

Source: Researcher, 2026

The constant term of -2.1356 is not significant since $t\text{-value}=-1.3754$ and $p\text{-value}=0.8348$. The coefficient term of 2.3645 of early civilization infers that 2.3645 units of early civilization explains only one unit of country languages and this coefficient is significant ($t=4.2541$, $p=.000$). The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that early civilization does not significantly influence country languages in Africa. The resulting equation of the linear regression model becomes;

$$\text{ContryLags} = 2.3645\text{EarlCivic}$$

Where ContryLags is country languages and EarlCivic is early civilization.

The Effect of Country Languages on Conflict Resolution

Country languages was regressed against conflict resolution and the regression equation revealed that there is positive relationship between the independent and the dependent variables as explained by the correlation coefficient of 74.2%. The coefficient of determination of R-Square was estimated at 66.4% is a testament that 66.4% of conflict resolution is explained by country languages and this explanation is significant as given by the F-value of 47.2643 and a significance p-value of 0.000 ($p=0.000$).

Table 7: Country Languages and Conflict Resolution

Model Summary							
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate			
1	.742 ^a	.664	.617	4.66313			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Country Languages							
ANOVA ^a							
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	87.7762	1	54.8861	47.2643	.000 ^b	
	Residual	33.3572	34	2.1483			
	Total	121.1334	35				
a. Dependent Variable: Conflict Resolution							

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b. Predictors: (Constant), Country Languages								
Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-2.0389	.4817		-1.2364	.7349	-.2536	1.4383
	Country Languages (CountryLags)	3.4674	2.1532	1.5375	3.1427	.0000	2.4327	4.3485

a. Dependent Variable: Conflict Resolution

Source: Researcher, 2026

The regression estimated a constant term of -2.0389 which is not significant ($t=-1.2364$, $p=0.7349$). The coefficient term of 3.4674 infers that 3.4674 units of country languages accounts for only one unit of conflict resolution which means the biggest proportion of conflict resolution is explained by other factors outside country languages. However the coefficient value of country languages of 3.4674 is significant ($t=3.1427$, $p=.000$). The study therefore rejects the hypothesis that country languages does not impact on conflict resolution in Africa. The resulting equation of the linear regression model becomes;

$$\text{ConflResolv} = 3.4674\text{CountryLags}$$

Where ConflResolv is conflict resolution and CountryLags is country languages.

The Effect of Early Civilization and Country Languages on Conflict Resolution

Table 8: Early Civilization and Country Languages on Conflict Resolution

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.9671 ^a	.9215	.8910	12.2836

a. Predictors: (Constant), Political Accountability, Jurisprudence

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	89.6614	1	77.6641	51.1367	.000 ^b
	Residual	37.3284	34	3.1561		
	Total	126.9898	35			

a. Dependent Variable: Conflict Resolution

b. Predictors: (Constant), Early Civilization, Country Languages

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-1.4359	1.6217		-.2783	.4179	0.4346	1.3476
	Early Civilization (EarlCivic)	3.3267	3.1384	2.3647	1.5356	.0000	1.3117	3.5346
	Country Languages (CountryLags)	1.1247	4.2689	1.3764	1.1247	.0000	1.1465	4.3254

a. Dependent Variable: Conflict Resolution

Source: Researcher, 2026

Early civilization and country languages were regressed against conflict resolution and the regression estimates revealed that there is a positive relationship between the two values as indicated by the correlation coefficient of 96.71%. Additionally, 92.15% (R-Square) of conflict resolution is explained by early civilization and country languages which is significant as denoted by F-value of 51.1367 and p-value of 0.000. The constant term of the regression was estimated at -1.4359 which was not significant ($t=-0.2783$, $p=0.4179$). The coefficients reveal that 3.3267 units of early civilization and 1.1247 units of country languages explain one unit of conflict resolution and they are both significant as denoted by ($t=1.5356$, $p=.000$) and ($t=1.1247$, $p=0.000$). Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis that early civilization and country languages do not significantly impact on conflict resolution in Africa. The regression equation from the regression model is stated as;

$$\text{ConflResolv} = 3.3267\text{EarlCivic} + 1.1247\text{CountryLags}$$

Where; ConlResolv is conflict resolution, EarlCivic is early civilization and CountryLags is country languages.

DISCUSSIONS

Descriptive statistics which were estimated revealed that conflict resolution, early civilization and country languages were found to have means of 1.8176, 3.2191 and 2.1619 respectively with standard deviations of 0.6250, 0.2364 and 0.1598 in that order. Data

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observations were skewed to the right, left and right respectively and was normally, not normally and normally distribute as listed. The means for the study variables were not too high except for early civilization and the variations were quite low. The regression equations estimated revealed that early civilization had a significant effect on conflict resolution with the explanatory power of 31.3% (R-Square=0.313) denoting that 68.7% is resolved without considering whether there were other conflicts that occurred in the past. Because 31.3% was found to be significant history should not be ignored when resolving conflicts. Early civilization was found to explain 44.7% of country languages which was significant (R-Square=0.447) an indication that countries have languages that they use and that they have always used in the past. However 55.3% of country languages is explained by other aspects other than history inferring that newer languages that are continuously emerging are important and should be added to the stock of those that already exist. Historically therefore different countries have different languages which they use for communication within and externally and therefore the evolution of languages should not be ignored when evaluating how far in the past countries want to evaluate their history. Country languages were found to be important determinants of conflict resolution as country languages explained 66.4% of conflict resolution which was found to be significant meaning the remaining 33.6% is explained by other factors other than country languages an inference that when resolving conflicts there is need to look beyond country languages. Aggregating history with country languages to influence conflict resolution revealed that both history and country languages explained 92.15% of conflict resolution and was found to be significant which means that only 7.85% of conflict resolution is explained by other aspects other than history and country languages.

CONCLUSIONS

Following the colonization of the African continent by the whites Africans were introduced to civilization and slowly by slowly they transited from being natives to becoming modernized. The study set to find out the influence of early civilization and country languages on conflict resolution in Africa. Pairing aspects revealed that their influence was significant. For example history significantly impacted on conflict resolution, country languages significantly influenced conflict resolution and collectively history and country languages significantly impacted on conflict resolution. Combining history and country languages increased the explanatory power of conflict resolution which infers that conflict resolution requires not only embracing country languages however many but also looking into history as to what conflicts arose in the past and how they were resolved to guide resolution of the current and future conflicts. Policy on conflict resolution should consider history, country languages and other aspects which have not been included in this study. Essentially the multiplicity and complexity of languages of African countries including the evolution of these languages should not be ignored when formulating policies so as to effectively resolve conflicts of African countries.

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